

Infrared Study of Some the Rare Earth Metal Chelates of β -Ketoimines

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Solid metal chelates of *N*-Benzoylacetone anthranilic acid and *N*-Benzoylacetone- β -alanine with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) have been synthesised. The magnetic susceptibility and infrared spectra are given in this communication. These chelates display 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The ligand exchange reactions between the metal chelates and EDTA have also been discussed. The presence of Nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in- β -position to the carboxylic group is responsible for the general similarity in the behavior of the two β -ketoimines.

A perusal of the literature shows that no systematic studies have been carried out so far on the chelates of *N*-Benzoylacetone anthranilic acid (H_2BA) and *N*-Benzoylacetone- β -alanine ($H_2B\beta A$) with Lanthanum (III), Cerium (III), Praseodymium (III), Neodymium (III) and Samarium (III). It is, therefore, of interest to carry out the physico-chemical investigation of these metal chelates.

Experimental

The synthesis of H_2BA and $H_2B\beta A$ have already been given in an earlier communication.¹

Synthesis of Rare Earth Chelates:—To an ethanolic solution of H_2BA or $H_2B\beta A$ (0.023*M*), a solution of rare earth metal nitrate (0.02*M*) in 80% ethyl alcohol was gradually added and the mixture was thoroughly stirred. Dilute ammonia (1:20) was then slowly added to this mixture until a flocculent yellowish green mass was formed. After continuous stirring for 6 hrs the solid mass was filtered under suction. It was washed with hot ethanol, dried in air and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. The yields and their analysis along with their magnetic moments are summarised in Table 1.

Chelates of H_2BA and $H_2B\beta A$ with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), and UO_2 (II) were also prepared by the known procedures^{2, 3, 4}. Elemental analysis and molecular weight determinations indicate 1:1 metal-ligand stoichiometry in these chelates.

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, YIELDS AND THE μ_{eff} VALUES OF H_2BA AND $H_2B\beta A$ CHELATES OF RARE EARTHS

Chelates and its composition	Yield %	Analysis				μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 303°K
		Found %		Calcd. %		
		N	Metal	N	Metal	
<i>H₂BA Chelates</i>						
LaC ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	87	4.09	19.71	4.11	19.10	—
CeC ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	76	4.00	20.27	4.05	20.42	2.25
PrC ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	72	4.02	20.19	4.05	20.27	3.37
NdC ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	78	3.72	20.38	3.98	20.51	3.52
SmC ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	80	3.71	21.07	3.94	21.19	1.55
<i>H₂BβA Chelates</i>						
LaC ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	86	4.48	22.96	4.65	23.07	—
CeC ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	78	4.49	23.11	4.64	23.23	2.27
PrC ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	71	4.44	23.17	4.63	23.33	3.38
NdC ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	80	4.39	23.73	4.60	23.81	3.49
SmC ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆	80	4.37	24.39	4.56	24.52	1.51

Ligand Replacement Reactions: The rare earth metal chelate (0.01*M*) synthesised above was added to a suspension of EDTA(0.01*M*) in water and the mixture was heated on a waterbath for nearly two hours. The solution was allowed to cool and the H_2BA or $H_2B\beta A$ set free was extracted into chloroform. The aqueous solution was concentrated to one-fourth of its original volume and allowed to cool to crystallise the EDTA-chelate of the rare earth. The crystals were separated by filtration and the filtrate on further concentration and cooling gave a second crop of the product. The chloroform extract of H_2BA or $H_2B\beta A$ was concentrated and cooled when the β -ketoimine crystals separated out. Their yield

recovered was found almost quantitative in all cases which indicate a complete exchange of ligands.

Using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer provided with sodium chloride prism, the I.R. Spectra of the chelates in Nujol mull were recorded. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined on a Gouy apparatus using mercury (II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate as the reference.

Results and Discussions :

The rare earth chelates do not possess sharp melting points and decompose without melting above 230° giving their oxides between 450° - 500° . These chelates are insoluble in water as well as in common organic solvents.

An examination of the infrared spectra of H_2BA

suggest the presence of $C=N$ and $C=O$ stretching vibrations respectively. In the spectra of the metal chelates these bands are broadened and no marked shift in the carbonyl frequency was observed. It has been reported that in the spectra of rare earth chelates of salicylaldehyde⁵ and acetoacetanilide⁶ shift in the carbonyl frequency is also not observed.

The weak band at 2750 cm^{-1} due to aldehydic C-H vibrations could neither be located in the spectra of Schiff bases nor in those of the metal chelates which might be due to the merger of C-H vibrations in the Nujol absorptions in this region. Thus based on the I. R. studies and other experimental evidences the rare earth chelates may be represented by the Figs. I and II.

I

II

WHERE M STANDS FOR La (III), Ce (III),
Pr (III), Nd (III) AND Sm (III)

and $H_2B\beta A$ has indicated two absorption bands at 3600 cm^{-1} and 1710 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the presence of $-OH$ and $-COOH$ groups. In all the metal chelates under study the weak band at 1710 cm^{-1} could not be located which indicates its elimination due to complexation. But in the spectra of the chelates (all having 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry, Table 1) the presence of only one band at 2900 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of a bonded $-OH$. This $-OH$ appears to be coordinated to the central rare earth metal atom in the chelate so as to complete its coordination number six.

H_2BA and $H_2B\beta A$ have also shown two more absorption bands at 1650 cm^{-1} and 1690 cm^{-1} which

As shown earlier the rare earth chelates undergo replacement reactions with EDTA which is a stronger chelating agent. Thus by the interaction of these chelates with EDTA in aqueous solution the corresponding EDTA chelates in pure form were obtained. By this technique we could succeed in preparing the EDTA chelates of Fe (II), Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Pd (II) and UO_2 (II). The I. R. Spectra of all such EDTA chelates were found to be identical with the reported spectra.

The lanthanum (III) chelates under examination were found to be diamagnetic. The magnetic moments (spin-free values, Table 1) obtained experimentally for the remaining rare earth chelates are in

good agreement with the values for typical lanthanide sulphates⁷.

These values suggest that the lanthanide ion acts, approximately as free ion, as far as the f-electrons are concerned. The similarity in the metal chelates derived from the ketoimines under study is, due to the presence of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in the β -position to the carboxylic group (Table 1, Figs, I and II).

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